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PRIN: PROGETTI DI RICERCA DI RILEVANTE INTERESSE NAZIONALE – Bando 2022 PNRR
Prot. P20224T9SK

PROMETEO

A **PRO**babilistic fra**ME**work for coas**T**al and harbor
d**E**fense in the c**O**ntext of climate change

D5.1

Project website

WP5 - Knowledge sharing & Capacity building

M5.1 - PROMETEO web-platform

O1 – O2 – O3 – O4

Task 5.1

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1. Introduction to the project web platform

The knowledge sharing & capacity building activities of WP5 consisted of a series of initiatives aimed at gathering insights from stakeholders and disseminating the project results to them. Among these initiatives, the project web-platform has been created to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice, by making available to stakeholders, researchers and general audience the procedures developed by PROMETEO.

The project website can be accessed at the following link: <https://www.progettoprometeo.eu/>.